

National Children's Science Congress 2022.

Project Title: Eco- Friendly Insecticide cum Pesticides Buggy

Focal Theme: Understanding Ecosystem for Health and Well-Being

Sub Theme: Technological innovation for ecosystem and health

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Category : Under Age Group

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PROBLEM

Agriculture produce **provides a major backing to both domestic and international markets**. An increase in rural purchasing power is very important for industrial development as two-thirds of the Indian population live in rural parts of India. But due to increased amount of growth of crops, pests like grasshoppers, lady bugs, Locusts and many more have come to feed on this produce. This in a way, has become a huge drawback in farmers' profits. They come up with destroyed and damaged crops which thus is not accepted by the purchasers. Plant pests and pathogens interfere with the growth and cause damage to cultivated and naturally growing plants. The interference and damage result in the failure of plants to reach their genetic potential. Pest insects can have adverse and damaging impacts on agricultural production and market access, the natural environment, and our lifestyle. Pest insects may cause problems **by damaging crops and food production, parasitizing livestock, or being a nuisance and health hazard to humans**. Since the dawn of agro-ecosystems nearly 10,000 years ago, farmers have had to compete with other organisms — namely insect pests, pathogens, weeds and wildlife— to ensure food security. These “biotic” (i.e. living) causes of crop loss can be just as harmful as “abiotic” (i.e. nonliving) stressors such as drought, extreme

temperatures, nutrient deficiencies, and high or low irradiance, often working in tandem to substantially limit crop production.

Such crop losses can be curtailed through various pest management strategies, which range from chemical and physical controls to biological and cultural strategies.

DAMAGED CROPS DUE TO PEST INSECTS

Brief Explanation to the Problem

In short, Productivity of crops grown for human consumption is

at risk due to the incidence of pests, especially weeds, pathogens and animal pests. Crop losses due to these harmful

organisms can be substantial and may be prevented, or reduced, by crop protection measures.

PROBLEM

(TEMPORARY SOLUTION BY THE PEOPLE)

As people often faced the issue of pest attacks, they needed to make an end to it. So, the Insecticides Act came into force with effect from August 1, 1971. Pesticides are to be compulsory registered under Insecticides Act and Rules at the Central level and license for their manufacture, formulation and sale are dealt with at the State level. With the enforcement of Insecticides Act and Rules

(PROBLEMS FACED BY THIS SOLUTION)

After this act was introduced, the farmers realized that the plants were turning unhealthy, and the fruit from the plants were bad for health. The soil was also getting affected by the pesticides. Our Team researched about these problems and this is what we found:

EFFECTS ON SOIL DUE TO PESTICIDES

1. Pesticides can contaminate soil, water, turf, and other **vegetation**. In addition to killing insects or weeds, pesticides can be toxic to a host of other organisms

including birds, fish, beneficial insects, and non-target plants.

2. Heavy treatment of soil with pesticides can **cause populations of beneficial soil microorganisms to decline.** According to the soil scientist Dr. Elaine Ingham, “If we lose both bacteria and fungi, then the soil degrades.

REASON FOR THE LOSS OF CROPS

Before we continued our `research, we made simple questions to break down our problem.

The insecticides include such chemicals as hydrogen cyanide, naphthalene, nicotine, and methyl bromide and are used mainly for killing insect pests of stored products or for fumigating nursery stock. One of the initial studies on HCN-producing pseudomonads (HPP), which concluded that HCN could be toxic for plant pathogens, was based on experiments that did not unambiguously exclude the activity of other antimicrobial compounds produced by these bacteria.

According to research and toxic or chemical substance used to eliminate a human or animals, has the same effect on plants. So, using

insecticides is practically killing them suddenly.

SOLUTION

We have come up with a solution which is completely eco – friendly- and easily available. We haven't made our project in an industrial scale. During our research we made sure that our solution will be a simple one which can be made through house hold materials.

To start with we have came up with 1 motive – stop insects from feeding on crops. But the solution by the people also damaged to crops. So had to make sure that the plants aren't also affected with our solution. So we tried our best to use as much eco-friendly materials are possible. After doing some research we came to know about two substances...

There are many advantages to using bicarbonate of soda, also known as baking soda, but the three main reasons are that **it is biodegradable, economical, and multi-purpose.** Above all, it has amazing properties.

We found out that camphor and baking soda are eco-friendly.

Being a green-plant product, **camphor is quite an eco-friendly source** and can be easily cultivated in as much quantity as required. Unlike any fossil/petroleum product, there is no fear of its ultimate shortage as it is a regenerative, reproducible source.

Camphor is an excellent natural insecticide. So the next time you see ants, bed bugs and mosquitoes at home you must use camphor. Ants: Dissolve a little camphor in water and sprinkle and sprinkle over the area and you will see the ants vanish immediately

We also found out that camphor and baking soda are effective natural pesticides

Sodium Bicarbonate, commonly known as Baking Soda **works well as an efficient and cost effective fungicide and insecticide.** It is actually registered with the EPA for use against certain plant fungi, powdery mildew.

Hence, we decided to use camphor and baking soda as our natural pesticides not only because they were ecofriendly but also because they were cost effective.

(COMBINATION OF TECHNOLOGY AND NATURE)

We brought up a concept of combining both Technology while supporting environment because we believe that supporting the nature with the latest updates is a very fruitful way of participating in the welfare of our society.

Starting up we have found two important substances which are going to be a key element for our Project namely – Baking Soda and Camphor (Kapoor). These two key elements are just as environment friendly and helps the plants for sustainable living and get ‘rid’ of the insects. These are easily available in markets and can be a very helpful part in our project.

WHY?

We have chosen this topic so that we can give value to the farmers needs and provide an ever- lasting solution. It will directly help and provide for us that if we care for such things. Including technology is also a way of contribution from us to this 21st century.

EXPERIMENTS

Without proceeding with our project with a blind eye we made some experiments to ensure the safety of the projects.

1. Camphor – Baking Soda reaction – First Up, we made sure that if there was any reaction between Camphor and Baking soda as e are going to combine both of them together to disperse the results. For that we took a steel container and some powdered camphor and baking soda. We heat them up and put them in a test tube. We added some distilled water and came to the conclusion that neither camphor nor baking soda is flammable or reactive to each other.

2. Is camphor and baking soda healthy for plants? – For this me and my team used baking soda solution in one plant and camphor solution with to another plant. As our solution

contains water praying these insecticides are watering the plants itself. We did this for one whole week and came up with the conclusion that both the substances are completely eco friendly and can eradicate insects.

(A)

(B)

WORKING OF THE PROJECT

Given above is a working model of our 'Eco-Friendly Insecticide cum Pesticides Buggy'. Here we have provided a 200 VOLT battery for long lasting performance and consistency. The circle

drawn in the middle is our pipe in which the baking soda cum camphor solution is exhaled and put into the crops. Here are 4 motors which will be connected to a tire for the movement of the buggy. The buggy will be running on a rechargeable battery so there will be no air pollution. The containers are of strong stainless steel which can be refilled at any time. There should be at least 500 mml of both the powdered solution there.

COST

4 Motors – 470 Rupees

200 VOLT Battery – 2400 Rupees

Stainless Steel Containers – 441 Rupees

Electric Dispensing pipe – 200 Rupees

Tire – 240 Rupees

Camphor – 600 rupees/kg

Baking Soda- 300 rupees/kg

TOTAL COST = 4651 rupees

We have made sure that our project is cost effective.

